

PROBLEMS OF TEACHING UZBEK LANGUAGE IN RUSSIAN GROUPS OF NONPHILOLOGICAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *In this article we will talk about the problems of teaching the Uzbek language in Russian groups of non-philological higher educational institutions. The author, relying on philological data and written sources, made clarifications on the basis of existing scientific literature and studied the peculiarities of the problems of teaching Uzbek language in Russian groups of non-philological higher education institutions.*

Keywords: *Higher Education, Russian groups, Uzbek language, technology, methods, problems of teaching.*

INTRODUCTION

The changes taking place around the world, the openness of access to information, have their impact on the educational sphere, the methods of teaching, the content of which also change the pedagogical and psychological purpose of its organization, the ability of students to operate independently, the rational use of the flow of information requires teaching. It follows from this that today's teacher should be able to create educational resources and effectively use the modern technologies of teaching them in practice, operate as a person with the skills to deliver the content of Science and the knowledge that is included in it to the students, interest the students to acquire knowledge, develop their creative abilities, self-analysis, work on. Because it has the ability to work with modern techniques, has a full understanding of the essence of the modern educational process, is able to solve problems that occur in situations that occur in the process of its activity, has sufficient skills and the need for training of a modern specialist is necessary to organize the educational process on a technological basis. To do this, technologies such as keys, WEB, communication information, interactive, multimedia, telecommunications or electronic learning, Smart Education are introduced into the learning process. Now, multimedia programs and electronic textbooks are becoming one of the main factors in the informatization of knowledge with the ability to perform various tasks quickly and at a short opportunity, display different images, prevail in didactic terms.

MAIN PART

In the higher education system, the use of Information Technology and multimedia teaching programs allows to improve the quality of language teaching, while psychologically creating conditions for the free application of one's knowledge to increase the interest of the student.

Today, in higher education institutions, the transition from E-learning (e-learning) to Smart Education (intelligent learning) is carried out. Smart education is a concept that includes all educational processes, as well as a wide range of methods and technologies used in these processes in the context of Education Smart Board (Smart Board), Smart Screen (Smart Screen),

Smart Phone (Smart Phone), Smart Table (smart table) Smart arrived. Each of these is the extra-curricular activity of the learner, as well as the opportunity to re-organize the lesson, as well as become an active participant in the educational process of studentstiradi [1].

The advantages of using smart technologies are that they have the advantages of revitalizing the audience environment, raising the mood, activating students, helping to organize work outside the educational process (concerts, holidays, literary evenings, watching educational videos), carrying out project activities, conducting online conferences (creating websites, publishing electronic magazines, placing poems, photos, etc.). Smart technology helps to carry out the activities of creative groups, work with talented children, increase students' personal competences and, finally, effective teaching in the humanities.

In this place, the question arises: what should be the modern lesson? Undoubtedly, it should be bright, visually and, of course, saturated with information, and teaching tools and methods should serve the development of creative potential, character formation, the outlook of participants in the educational process. The main task of the modern teacher is not to give the data ready and to verify that the exercises are performed correctly, but to independently search for the necessary information from various sources (textbook, encyclopedia, dictionary, Internet resource), solve the problems that caused the shooting, to teach to protect his position. To do this, the teacher must be in harmony with the Times and use in his lesson not only modern methods and methods, but also the latest works in the field of computer technology.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

In our country, the sphere of Higher Education has been paid special attention since the early years of independence. In particular, the establishment of teaching Uzbek language as a state language in non-Uzbek groups served as an important factor in fulfilling the requirements of the law "on the state language". Because in Uzbekistan there are more than 130 representatives of different nationalities and nationalities. Our state undertakes to respect their national traditions, culture and native languages. In addition, the introduction of the article "the state language of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the Uzbek language" in the main encyclopaedia of our state has served to increase the prestige of the Uzbek language and its reputation as the state language [2].

Due to this constitutional duty and duties, education in Uzbekistan has been carried out in 7 languages. The establishment of non-Uzbek groups with the teaching of their native language as well as teaching Uzbek as the state language served as an important program in fulfilling the requirements of our Basic Law and the law "on the state language" in our country. The state educational standard and educational programs for teaching Uzbek language as the state language in schools where education is conducted in other languages, formation of certain competences in the students of this subject, the objectives and objectives of this subject are defined.

According to the request of the DTS, the main purpose of teaching Uzbek language is embodied in two compartments. 1. Speech competence is the ability to listen, understand, read, speak and write, that is, to acquire communication skills. 2. Linguistic competence-refers to the acquisition of knowledge and types of speech activity (listening, understanding, reading, speaking, writing), in order to acquire sufficient knowledge to be able to use language material (phonetics, lexicology, semantics) and tools in speech [3].

The standard sets out the language material, language tools and grammatical knowledge, the necessary skills to be formed on each type of speech activity.

It requires appropriate use of literary language capabilities in the correct pronunciation and writing of the word and word forms studied, the correct formation of the word in terms of grammatics, appropriate selection of words, the correct assessment of the syntactic-stylistic point of view, the formation of sentences and the determination of the tone of speech [4].

In order to accomplish these goals and tasks, textbooks of the Uzbek language provide information on grammatics, as well as literary and artistic texts for the development of speech competence, information on the life and creativity of Uzbek poet-u writers. The reader who gets acquainted with this information will see rich samples of the Uzbek literary language and literature and develop speech skills from the Uzbek language. That is, along with linguistic competence, speech competence is formed, which creates the necessary knowledge in science.

The teacher's pedagogical skills, as well as sufficient theoretical knowledge of the subject, contribute to the wider opening of this topic. However, it is natural that it is not justified to give knowledge to a student only by speaking dry theoretical data, or by writing a lecture. Because Bugun's student is curious in all respects and loves to see and shine. Therefore, the methods that the teacher uses in explaining the topic occupy an important place in this regard.

Above, we are confident that such teaching methods, which have absorbed an innovative pedagogical spirit in themselves, will not only increase the speech competence of students, but will also help them in the deep vein of the qualities of independent research and aspiration. But we must not forget about the circumstances or circumstances in which these methods and techniques are used, how they can be understood to the students, and how they relate to the pedagogical skills of the teacher.

CONCLUSION

Such lesson technologies, which are passed on the basis of modern education in the nophylogological higher educational institutions, can help students to demonstrate their abilities from all sides, and, most importantly, to develop their speech skills and competences from the Uzbek language in Russian groups. There is no doubt that the lessons in this method will help bring a new era man to perfection in his upbringing.

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